

A study on the effect of dye sensitizers on nanostructured GaAs/PS based DSSCs

K.Gangadevi¹, K.Ramachandren² and **R. Srinivasan^{1,*}**

¹ *Department of Physics, Thiagarajar College, Madurai – 625 009*

² *Department of Physics, The Gandhigram Rural University, Dindigul – 624 302.*

Corresponding author:r_srini2067@yahoo.co.in , 9443148581

Abstract

Nanostructured porous silicon (PS) sample were prepared at a current density of 30 mA/cm² for etching periods 60 minute. The Gallium Arsenide (GaAs) is used as a nanofillers to fill the PS samples. The XRD patterns reveal the formation of PS and GaAs on PS. Then the photoanodes were prepared by sensitizing the surfaces of these PS+GaAs samples with various dyes such as chloroaluminium phthalocyanine (ClAlPc), N7 and Eosin – Y (EY). The bandgap of the samples foundd from Photoluminescence (PL) spectrum are in the range of 1.9 – 2.0 eV. The photocurrent and photovoltage of the cells weres measured using Keithely source meter. The maximum conversion efficiency of 2.8% is observed and results are discussed.

Keywords: Porous Silicon, GaAs, Photoluminescence, DSSC.